

VARIABLE NEIGHBORHOOD SEARCH FOR THE P-NEXT CENTER PROBLEM WITH DISCOUNT FACTOR

JELENA TASIĆ¹, ZORICA STANIMIROVIĆ², ZORICA DRAŽIĆ³

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mathematics, Belgrade, jelena.tasic@matf.bg.ac.rs, 0009-0002-0145-6985

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mathematics, Belgrade, zorica.stanimirovic@matf.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0001-5658-4111

³ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mathematics, Belgrade, zorica.drazic@matf.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0002-3434-6734

Abstract: *The p-next center problem (PNCP) is an extension of the well-known p-center problem, which captures the situation when one or more centers suddenly fail due to some technical problem. If a user is faced with the failure of its primary center, it is being redirected to its backup center - the center that is closest to the primary one. The goal of the PNCP is to minimize the maximum distance that a user must travel to its backup center via the primary center. In practice, the distance that the user travels is often expressed in travel cost or travel time, and the communication between the centers is cheaper or faster. In order to capture this real-world situation, we involve a discount factor for the travel cost or time between the centers in the objective function of the classical PNCP. A metaheuristic method based on variable neighborhood search is used as a solution method for the considered variant of the PNCP. The set of computational experiments on instances from the literature is performed to investigate the impact of the discount factor on the obtained solutions and the corresponding objective function values.*

Keywords: *Location analysis, p-next center problem, Discount factor, Technical failure, Emergency service network, Variable neighborhood search.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The p-center problem (PCP) introduced in (Hakimi, 1965) is one of the most studied NP-hard combinatorial optimization problems in the literature, see (Biazaran and Seyedinezhad, 2009; Celik Turkoglu and Erol Genevois, 2020). Starting from the set of locations of users and potential centers, the goal of the PCP is to open exactly p centers in order to minimize the maximum distance user travels to its nearest center. An extension of the PCP that covers situations where some of the centers suddenly fail is introduced in (Albareda-Sambola et al., 2015) and named the p-next center problem (PNCP). In the PNCP, the number of centers to be opened is set to p and each user is assigned to its closest opened center (primary center). In the case of a failure of its primary center, a user proceeds to an opened center that is closest to the primary one, denoted as backup center. It is assumed that a customer will pass through the primary center to reach its backup center. The goal of the PNCP is to find locations for opening exactly p centers such that the maximum distance from a user to its backup center via the primary center is minimized. The PNCP finds its application in the planning of emergency service networks (finding optimal locations of ambulances, hospitals, fire stations, police stations), but also in the optimizing customer service networks (determining optimal locations for ATMs in urban areas, opening gas stations of a gas distribution company, planning the network of supermarkets or drugstores of the same company, etc.).

There are several studies in the literature that deal with the PNCP. In (Lopez-Sanchez et al., 2019), a Greedy Randomized Adaptive Procedure (GRASP), a Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) and their hybridization (GRASP-VNS) were proposed to solve the PNCP. Computational experiments on instances with up to 200 nodes showed that the hybrid GRASP-VNS approach had the best performance. In the paper (Ristić et al., 2021), the authors presented the Filtered VNS method (FVNS), which was shown to be efficient in solving pmed instances with up to 200 nodes, and also the Additional instances with up to 900 nodes, introduced in the same study. In (Tasić, 2024), a Skewed VNS method (SVNS) was proposed for the PNCP, and it was shown that the SVNS reaches or improves the best FVNS solutions on both pmed and Additional data sets. Three variants of a Multi-Parent Biased Random-Key Genetic Algorithm with Implicit Path-Relinking (BRKGA) were introduced in (Londe et al., 2021) to solve the PNCP. The computational results on the set of 416 instances with up to 500 nodes showed the ability of BRKGAs to find excellent quality solutions, but with a significant running time consumption. A variant of the local search (LS) method with two strategies used to exploit the flat subspaces

was proposed in (Mousavi, 2023). Computational experiments on pmed instances with up to 200 nodes showed the advantages of the LS-based heuristic over the approaches from (López-Sánchez et al., 2019) in solving the PNCP. The study (Zhang et al., 2022) presented a weighting-based tabu search algorithm (WTS), which was tested on pmed-based instances with up to 900 nodes. The results of the comparative study indicate that WTS outperforms GRASP-VNS and the three BRKGA methods on the set of PNCP instances used in all three studies. A modified Basic VNS method proposed in (Ristić et al., 2023) was shown to be superior over all previous state-of-the-art PNCP methods in terms of solution quality on instances with up to 900 nodes. In addition, the authors introduced two new data sets of PNCP instances with up to 1000 and 2500 nodes, respectively.

In this study, we consider a variant of the PNCP that better reflects the situation in practice. Once the emergency or service centers are opened, efficient and reliable communication channels between them are also provided. Therefore, it is natural to assume that communication between the centers is more efficient (regarding travel time or transportation costs) than communication between a user and a center. For this reason, we involve parameter $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ in the PNCP model, which represents the discount factor for the travel cost (or time) that a user travels from its primary to backup center. This problem is named the PNCP with discount factor and it belongs to the class of NP-hard problems, as a variant of PNCP that has been shown to be NP-hard (Albareda-Sambola et al., 2015). Due to the complexity of the problem under consideration, we use a Basic variant of the Variable Neighborhood Search metaheuristic (BVNS) as a solution approach. The choice of the solution method was motivated by previous successful VNS implementations for the PNCP (Ristić et al., 2021; Ristić et al., 2023; Tasić, 2024) and the necessity of having an efficient algorithm that is capable to solve instances of large dimensions. The elements of the proposed BVNS have been modified according to the characteristics of the problem considered. The BVNS uses Move Evaluation and Update procedures instead of the classical swap and/or update from scratch, which increases the efficiency of the algorithm.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, mathematical formulation of the PNCP with discount factor is given. Section 3 explains the implementation steps of the BVNS metaheuristic for the problem under consideration. In Section 4, we present computational results obtained on pmed and Additional instances from the literature. The summary of the contributions and some future work directions are given in Section 5.

2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The p -next center problem with discount factor is defined on an undirected weighted graph $G = (A, E)$, where $A = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ denotes the set of n nodes in the network, which represent both the locations of users and potential centers, and $E = \{(i, j) : i, j \in A, i \neq j\}$ is the set of edges. Each edge $(i, j) \in E$ has a weight d_{ij} corresponding to the travel cost or time along that edge. For each pair of nodes $i, j \in A, i \neq j$, the distance $d(i, j)$ is calculated as the length of the shortest path (in terms of travel cost or time) from i to j , and thus the distances satisfy the triangle inequality. The number of centers to be opened is set to p . Each user is assigned to its primary center, which is the closest center (in terms of travel cost or time), while the backup center is the closest center to its primary one. The parameter $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ denotes the discount factor that multiplies the travel cost or time from a primary center to a backup center.

The goal of the problem is to find a set of centers $P \subset A$ with cardinality p such that the maximum travel cost (or time) from a user to its assigned backup center is minimized. The travel cost from a user to its allocated backup center is calculated as the sum of the travel cost from the user to its primary center and the travel cost from the primary center to its backup center, multiplied by the discount factor γ . More precisely, the objective is

$$\min_{P \subset A, |P|=p} f(P), \quad (1)$$

where

$$f(P) = \max_{i \in A} \left\{ \min_{j \in P} d(i, j) + \min_{j' \in \operatorname{argmin}_{j \in P} d(i, j)} \min_{k \in P, k \neq j'} \gamma \cdot d(j', k) \right\}. \quad (2)$$

The formulation presented here is obtained from the PNCP formulation proposed in the paper (Albareda-Sambola et al., 2015) by including the discount factor γ in the second part of the function $f(P)$. In (Albareda-Sambola et al., 2015), the authors gave a formal proof that the PNCP is NP-hard, and therefore, the considered PNCP variant with discount factor is also NP-hard.

In order to graphically illustrate the effects of using the discount factor γ , let us consider a small example with $n = 10$ locations given by their coordinates in the plane and $p = 3$ centers to be opened. The opened centers are marked with ■, the users are marked with ●, while the assignments of the customers to the centers are denoted with black lines (see Figure 1). In the optimal solution of the PNCP, placing centers at locations 3, 5, and 8 results in objective function value of 5.89, which differs from the solution obtained with a discount factor of $\gamma = 0.1$, where centers are placed at locations 3, 5, and 9, and the corresponding objective value is 3.05. When the discount factor is slightly increased to $\gamma = 0.2$, the resulting optimal solution again differs from both previous cases, with centers at locations 3, 5, and 10, and an objective function value of 3.28.

Figure 1: Comparison of the optimal solutions for (a) PNCP, (b) PNCP with $\gamma = 0.1$ (c) PNCP with $\gamma = 0.2$ on a small-size network

3. THE PROPOSED BASIC VARIABLE NEIGHBORHOOD SEARCH

Variable Neighborhood Search is a metaheuristic introduced by Mladenović and Hansen (Mladenović and Hansen, 1997), based on the idea of systematic changes of neighborhood structures during the search. Up to now, many variants of VNS metaheuristics have been proposed in the literature and applied to a wide range of optimization problems. Examples of successful applications of VNS-based methods to the p -center problem and its variants can be found in the literature. For example, VNS heuristics have been developed for solving the p -center problem in (Mladenović et al., 2003), the probabilistic p -center problem in (Martínez-Merino et al., 2017), the unconditional and conditional vertex p -center problems in (Irawan et al., 2016), the capacitated vertex p -center problem in (Quevedo-Orozco and Ríos-Mercado, 2015), the p -next center problem in (López-Sánchez et al., 2019; Ristić et al., 2021; Ristić et al., 2023; Tasić, 2024), the conditional p -next center problem in (Tasić et al., 2025), etc.

To solve the PNCP with discount factor, we adapt the concept of the Basic Variable Neighborhood Search (BVNS) method described in Algorithm 1. The BVNS method starts from a randomly generated solution and the set of predefined neighborhood structures $N_k, k = 1, \dots, k_{max}$. The solution of the problem is represented by an integer vector x of length p containing the indices of the locations with established centers. The solution is feasible if the corresponding p -dimensional vector contains indices that are mutually different. The indices of the locations with established centers are obtained from the integer vector x and each user is assigned to its nearest center (the primary one), while the user's backup center is determined as the one closest to its primary center. Once the primary and backup centers are known for each user, the objective function value $f(x)$ can be easily calculated. In the proposed BVNS, the neighborhood $N_k, k = 1, \dots, k_{max}$ of a solution x consists of all feasible solutions x' satisfying $d(x, x') = k$, where $d(x, x')$ is defined as the total number of distinct locations chosen as centers for the solutions x and x' .

An iteration of BVNS consists of two main phases - Shaking and Local Search, as well as the decision about the neighborhood change (Move or Not step). In the Shaking phase, a feasible solution x' is randomly selected from the current neighborhood $N_k(x)$. More precisely, k locations that do not belong to the solution x are randomly selected to replace k randomly selected centers from x , and thus a neighbor $x' \in N_k(x)$ is obtained. The procedure Update is executed to find the primary and backup centers for each user in the new solution x' and to calculate its objective function value efficiently. During the Local Search phase, which is based on the Move evaluation and Update procedures, the neighborhood $N_1(x')$ is explored to reach a local optimum x'' . For a given $i \notin x'$, the Move evaluation procedure finds a center j in the current solution x' to be exchanged with i such that the value of $f((x' \cup \{i\}) \setminus \{j\})$ is minimal. Swapping a specific pair of locations (i, j') can affect users in three different ways: (a) users may remain unaffected, (b) users may start using the new center i as their primary or backup center (if it is closer than their current primary or backup center), and (c) users may lose their existing primary or backup center and need to be reallocated. Taking all three scenarios into account, the potential swap of element $i \notin x$ with each element $j' \in x$ can be evaluated efficiently using specific auxiliary structures, allowing the best candidate $j \in x$ for elimination to be identified. This is achieved by considering each location only once and examining possible outcomes for that location: adopting i as the primary or backup center or changing its current primary and/or backup center. In this way, a complexity of $O(n)$ can be achieved for the Move Evaluation procedure.

The Local Search procedure examines each potential center $i \notin x'$ and applies the Move evaluation procedure to find the best candidate $j \in x'$ to be replaced by i . Once the best exchange pair is found, the procedure Update

performs the swap that leads to the improved solution, updates the set of primary and backup centers for each user and calculates the objective function value of the improved solution. The steps are repeated as long as an improvement can be found, and the output of the Local Search phase is the local optimum x'' .

If the local optimum x'' obtained from the Local Search phase improves the objective function value of the current solution x , the algorithm moves on to this new solution and continues the search from there. Otherwise, the order of neighborhood to be explored is increased by 1 and the algorithm moves on to the Shaking phase. The algorithm is executed until the stopping criterion (the maximal number of iterations) is met.

Algorithm 1 BVNS algorithm

```

1: Initialization: select the set of neighborhoods  $N_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, k_{max}$ 
2: Randomly generate a feasible initial solution  $x$  and set  $f \leftarrow f(x)$ 
3: while the stopping criterion is not met do
4:    $k \leftarrow 1$ 
5:   while  $k \leq k_{max}$  and the stopping criterion is not met do
6:      $x' \leftarrow Shaking(x, k)$  ▷ Shaking phase
7:      $x'' \leftarrow Local\_Search(x')$  ▷ Local Search phase
8:     if  $f(x'') < f$  then ▷ Move or Not step
9:        $x \leftarrow x'', f \leftarrow f(x''), k \leftarrow 1$ 
10:    else
11:       $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
12:    end if
13:  end while
14: end while

```

4. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The BVNS metaheuristic for solving the p -next center problem with discount factor is implemented in the C++ programming language. The computational experiments were performed on a desktop computer with Intel Core i7-11700 3.6GHz processor and 16GB RAM in a 64bit Windows 10 environment. Experimental results were obtained on a set of 50 small-size pmed instances from (Beasley, 1990) with up to 50 vertices and a set of Additional instances with up to 900 vertices from (Ristić et al., 2021). Values of 0.1, 0.4 and 0.6 were used for the parameter γ , representing different values of the discount factor. The proposed BVNS was executed 20 times for each test instance, each time starting from a different random initial solution. The maximum number of BVNS iterations was used as the stopping criterion: 500 for the instances with $n \leq 50$ and 5000 for instances with $100 \leq n \leq 900$. For all instances, the value of parameter k_{max} was set to 5. The quality of the results obtained with the proposed BVNS method was evaluated by comparing them with the optimal and suboptimal solutions obtained with the exact solver CPLEX 22.1.0, which uses the mathematical formulation from Section 2. The execution time of the CPLEX solver was limited to 2 hours for each tested instance.

Table 1: The summary of results obtained by CPLEX and BVNS on pmed ($n \leq 50$) and Additional ($100 \leq n \leq 900$) instances

Inst	n	#Inst	γ	CPLEX			BVNS	
				#Opt	#Feas	avg.t(s)	%bk	avg.t(s)
pmed	$n \leq 50$	50	0.1	50	-	56.35	100%	0.04
Additional	$100 \leq n \leq 900$	40	0.1	0	16	7200	100%	17.45
pmed	$n \leq 50$	50	0.4	50	-	18.90	100%	0.03
Additional	$100 \leq n \leq 900$	40	0.4	2	16	6602	100%	12.67
pmed	$n \leq 50$	50	0.6	50	-	11.73	98%	0.03
Additional	$100 \leq n \leq 900$	40	0.6	3	16	6170.63	100%	79.48

Table 1 contains an overview of the results of the CPLEX solver and the proposed BVNS. The columns Inst, n , #Inst, and γ contain the name of the data set, the dimension of instances belonging to this data set, the total number of tested instances, and the value of the discount factor. For each different γ , the number of optimal solutions (#Opt) and feasible solutions (#Feas) obtained by CPLEX are given. For the BVNS, we present the percentage of success in reaching the best known solution (%bk), i.e., the optimal solution for instances solved to optimality by CPLEX and the best solution obtained by either CPLEX or BVNS for the remaining instances. The columns labeled avg.t contain the average total execution time (in seconds) for CPLEX solver and BVNS

method, respectively. Note that the avg.t values are calculated only for instances where CPLEX reached either the optimal or the feasible solution. From the data presented in Table 1, it can be seen that CPLEX successfully reaches all optimal solutions for small-size pmed instances. However, in the case of the Additional set with larger instance dimensions, CPLEX could not even reach a feasible solution for more than half of the tested instances due to time or memory limits (out of memory). On the other hand, BVNS reaches all optimal solutions obtained by CPLEX, except for one instance (*pmed3_50_20* in case when $\gamma = 0.6$), and outperforms feasible CPLEX solutions in most cases in significantly less computing time.

Table 2: The detailed results obtained by BVNS on pmed ($n \leq 50$) and Additional ($100 \leq n \leq 900$) instances

<i>n</i>	#Inst	UB	BVNS								
			$\gamma = 0.1$			$\gamma = 0.4$			$\gamma = 0.6$		
			avg.f	avg.t	sav(%)	avg.f	avg.t	sav(%)	avg.f	avg.t	sav(%)
10	5	106.6	50.68	<0.01	53.99	72.88	<0.01	33.99	85.84	<0.01	21.87
20	10	117.7	68.46	0.01	42.73	89.04	0.01	25.10	99.36	0.01	16.27
30	10	134.9	85.96	0.03	36.20	102.5	0.02	23.99	115.06	0.02	14.77
40	15	121.27	79.13	0.04	36.22	95.39	0.04	22.62	105.2	0.04	14.16
50	10	107.7	70.35	0.07	34.91	85.02	0.06	21.49	92.26	0.06	14.60
100	5	131	94	2.02	29.61	107.12	1.78	19.70	114.60	1.73	14.26
200	5	82.60	55.38	8.10	35.35	63.64	7.10	25.33	69.36	6.09	17.66
300	5	58.60	39.70	19.10	33.96	44.52	16.29	25.44	47.20	15.46	20.68
400	5	44.40	31.08	34.69	31.64	35.28	29.09	21.42	37.28	29.87	16.74
500	5	41	27.62	56.53	33.39	31.32	48.35	24.13	34.24	46.83	16.93
600	5	43.60	24.40	84.31	43.17	27.68	72.31	35.29	32.06	67.26	26.13
700	4	42.50	23.28	66.30	38.74	25.95	59.69	31.11	31.05	55.38	20.18
800	3	37	25.47	47.35	31.54	28.13	43.15	24.19	29.60	46.35	20.10
900	3	45.67	23.40	67.36	40.79	26.73	56.02	33.04	32.53	53.45	23.23
Total					37.32			25.20			17.23

Table 2 shows the results obtained by the proposed BVNS metaheuristic for all considered instances. The first two columns of Table 2 contain the dimension of the instance group - *n* and the total number of instances in this group - #Inst. In the next column, denoted as UB, we present the average objective value of the best known PNCP solutions on the same group of instances. Note that the objective values of the PNCP problem are obtained for $\gamma = 1$ and represent the upper bound of the objective function values for the PNCP with discount factors $\gamma < 1$. For each different γ value, the data related to the BVNS solutions is presented in the following columns: avg.f - the average value of the objective function calculated over all instances in the considered group (for each instance in the group, the best solution value across 20 BVNS executions was used for calculating avg.f), avg.t - the average total execution time (given in seconds) and avg.sav - the average saving achieved with the given γ compared to UB (given in percentages). The results presented in Table 2 show that the proposed BVNS algorithm provides high quality solutions in short execution times considering the dimensions of the tested instances. From the last row of the Table 2, it can be concluded that the average total savings are 17.23% if the efficiency of communication between the centers was increased by 40% ($\gamma = 0.6$ instead of $\gamma = 1$). In the case of $\gamma = 0.4$ and $\gamma = 0.1$, the savings are 25.20% and 37.32%, respectively.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes the PNCP with discount factor, which represents a variant of the well-known PNCP. The discount factor $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ applies to the travel cost or time between the centers in the objective function. Due to the NP-hardness of the considered problem, the BVNS metaheuristic is implemented as solution method. The solution encoding, neighborhood structures, and other elements of the proposed BVNS are adapted to the problem's characteristics. Experimental study was conducted on pmed and Additional instances from the literature, and the obtained BVNS results were compared with the results of the exact CPLEX solver that uses the mathematical formulation of the problem. As it was expected, the CPLEX does not provide even feasible solutions for larger dimensions of the problem ($n > 400$). On the other hand, BVNS achieves all optimal solutions obtained by CPLEX (with exception of one case) in significantly less execution time than CPLEX, and the same or better solutions in the cases when CPLEX returns only feasible solutions. For large instances, which are out of reach of CPLEX due to limited time or memory resources, the implemented BVNS provides solutions of good quality in a relatively short execution time, considering the dimensions of the instances.

Further research may include the implementation of new metaheuristic algorithms, the extension of the model by adding new constraints, testing instances with larger dimensions, and additional adjustments of the components of the metaheuristic methods according to the characteristics of the considered problem.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research of the authors was partially funded by University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mathematics through the grant by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (the contract no 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200104)

LITERATURE

- Albareda-Sambola, M., Hinojosa, Y., Marín, A., & Puerto, J. (2015). When centers can fail: A close second opportunity. *Computers & Operations Research*, 62, 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2015.01.002>
- Beasley, J. E. (1990). OR-library: Distributing test problems by electronic mail. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 41(11), 1069–1072. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jors.1990.166>
- Biazaran, M., & SeyediNezhad, B. (2009). Facility location: Concepts, models, algorithms and case studies. In R. Z. Farahani & M. Hekmatfar (Eds.). *Physica Heidelberg*.
- Celik Turkoglu, D., & Erol Genevois, M. (2020). A comparative survey of service facility location problems. *Annals of Operations Research*, 292, 399–468. <https://doi.org/0.1007/s10479-019-03385-x>
- Hakimi, S. L. (1965). Optimum distribution of switching centers in a communication network and some related graph theoretic problem. *Operations Research*, 13(3), 462–475. <https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.13.3.462>
- Irawan, C. A., Salhi, S., & Drezner, Z. (2016). Hybrid meta-heuristics with vns and exact methods: Application to large unconditional and conditional vertex p-center problems. *Journal of Heuristics*, 22(4), 507–537. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10732-014-9277-7>
- Londe, M. A., Andrade, C. E., & Pessoa, L. S. (2021). An evolutionary approach for the p-next center problem. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 175, 114728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2021.114728>
- López-Sánchez, A. D., Sánchez-Oro, J., & Hernández-Díaz, A. G. (2019). GRASP and VNS for solving the p-next center problem. *Computers & Operations Research*, 104, 295–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2018.12.017>
- Martínez-Merino, L. I., Albareda-Sambola, M., & Rodríguez-Chía, A. M. (2017). The probabilistic p-center problem: Planning service for potential customers. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 262(2), 509–520. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2017.03.043>
- Mladenović, N., & Hansen, P. (1997). Variable neighborhood search. *Computers & Operations Research*, 24(11), 1097–1100. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-0548\(97\)00031-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-0548(97)00031-2)
- Mladenović, N., Labbé, M., & Hansen, P. (2003). Solving the p-center problem with tabu search and variable neighborhood search. *Networks: An International Journal*, 42(1), 48–64. <https://doi.org/10.1002/net.10081>
- Mousavi, S. R. (2023). Exploiting flat subspaces in local search for p-center problem and two fault-tolerant variants. *Computers & Operations Research*, 149, 106023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2022.106023>
- Quevedo-Orozco, D. R., & Ríos-Mercado, R. Z. (2015). Improving the quality of heuristic solutions for the capacitated vertex p-center problem through iterated greedy local search with variable neighborhood descent. *Computers & Operations Research*, 62, 133–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2014.12.013>
- Ristić, D., Mladenovic, N., Todosijević, R., & Urošević, D. (2021). Filtered variable neighborhood search method for the p-next center problem. *International Journal for Traffic and Transport Engineering*, 11(2), 294–309. [https://doi.org/10.7708/ijtte.2021.11\(2\).09](https://doi.org/10.7708/ijtte.2021.11(2).09)
- Ristić, D., Urošević, D., Mladenović, N., & Todosijević, R. (2023). Solving the p-second center problem with variable neighborhood search. *Computer Science and Information Systems*, 20(1), 95–115. <https://doi.org/10.2298/CSIS210804049R>
- Tasić, J. (2024). An efficient solution approach to the p-next center problem. *Matematički Vesnik*, 76(1), 66–83. <https://doi.org/10.57016/MV-RBJS4362>
- Tasić, J., Dražić, Z., & Stanimirović, Z. (2025). A VNS method for the conditional p-next center problem. *Computers & Operations Research*, 175, 106916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2024.106916>
- Zhang, Q., Su, Z., Lü, Z., & Yang, L. (2022). A weighting-based tabu search algorithm for the p-next center problem. In L. De Raed (Ed.), *Proceedings of the thirty-first international joint conference on artificial intelligence (ijcai-22)* (pp. 4828–4834). International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence.